

Research article

Tibetic terms for ‘sow’ and ‘boar’ in re-interpretation and analogy: From ‘female pig’ to ‘pig-mother’ and then to ‘pig-father’

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Abstract: This article discusses word forms for ‘sow’ and ‘boar’ in Tibetic languages in the eastern Tibetosphere, focusing on the re-interpretation of *phag ma* ‘sow’ and its ‘newly generated’ male counterpart *phag pha* ‘boar’. The former appears widely in the target area, whereas the latter only appears in its southernmost part. The suffix *ma* in *phag ma* was originally a female noun suffix. However, in several dialects in the southern Khams region, *ma* has been re-interpreted as a morpheme denoting ‘mother’; this triggered the generation of its parallel form, *phag pha*, literally ‘pig-father’, as a result of analogy. This re-interpretation is a result of a subclassification of ‘sow’ in the southernmost area: ‘sow with piglets’ and ‘sow without piglets’. The word form *phag ma* denotes the former; in a sense, *phag ma* is easily interpreted as ‘pig-mother’, distinguished from a ‘female pig’. Moreover, the data include the word form *phag a ma* ‘sow’, literally ‘pig mother’. Therefore, there is high potential for a re-interpretation of the word form *phag ma* as ‘pig-mother’.*

Keywords: Tibetic; Khams Tibetan; lexical derivation; animal terms; analogy

1. Introduction

Nominal derivation of markers denoting gender difference (‘male’ and ‘female’) in animal terms has so far received attention in the dialectology and geolinguistics of Sinitic languages (Cao 2008:76, Yagi 2019). A similar topic concerning the morphological process of animal terms is also found in Tibetic languages, displaying great variation. In Literary Tibetan (LT), we find two patterns: the use of different roots

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and a general term plus a derived form, as in Table 1. LT forms are transcribed with the method of de Nebesky-Wojkowitz (1956).

Table 1 Literary Tibetan animal terms.

animal	general term	male	female
yak	<i>zog / nor / phyugs</i>	<i>g.yag</i>	<i>'bri</i>
horse	<i>rta</i>	<i>rta pho</i>	<i>rgod ma</i>
chicken	<i>bya</i>	<i>bya pho</i>	<i>bya mo</i>
pig	<i>phag</i>	<i>pho phag</i>	<i>mo phag</i>

As Table 1 shows, the terms for ‘yak’ and ‘horse’ use different roots for ‘male’ and ‘female’, whereas the terms for ‘chicken’ and ‘pig’ use derivational morphology. Furthermore, the latter type exhibits a different affixation pattern depending on the animal. Both ‘chicken’ and ‘pig’ use the same gender-determining morphemes *pho* ‘male’ and *mo* ‘female’; however, the terms for ‘chicken’ use them as a suffix, those for ‘pig’ as a prefix. There are variations in LT; for example, *phag ma* ‘sow’, a suffixed type, is also attested. Cf. Beyer (1992:123-126).

Suzuki (2019b), expanding the discussions in Suzuki (2007, 2012), further discusses word forms for the three ‘pig’ terms ‘boar’, ‘sow’, and ‘piglet’ in Tibetic languages spoken in the eastern Tibetosphere, and displays linguistic maps of these words with a classification of the word forms. Based on Suzuki’s (2019b) data, this article aims to discuss a possibility of analogy in word formation for ‘boar’ and ‘sow’ in Tibetic languages, especially those spoken in the Tibetosphere in Yunnan.

This article aims to provide a more detailed explanation of specific word forms for ‘sow’ (female adult pig) and ‘boar’ (male adult pig), based on the data in Suzuki (2019b). Before discussing cases in Tibetic languages in the eastern Tibetosphere, I explain the basic Literary Tibetan lexemes. As Table 1 shows, the general term for ‘pig’ is *phag*; in a dictionary, *phag* designates ‘pig’ as a symbol such as the year, which is in contrast with *phag pa*, reserved for ‘pig’ as a living animal. The term for ‘boar’ consists of two morphemes, *pho phag* and *phag pho*, in which *pho* means ‘male’. The term for ‘sow’ also consists of two morphemes; however, it has more combinations than ‘boar’: *mo phag*, *phag mo*, and *phag ma*. The morphemes *mo* and *ma* both denote ‘female’ as a part of terms for animate objects. Note that these morphemes also function as nominal suffixes and nominalisers together with *po*, *pa*, *bo*, and *ba*, for example, *gru mo* ‘elbow’, *nyi ma* ‘sun’, *sdong po* ‘trunk’, *smug pa* ‘fog’, *chu bo* ‘river’, and *ser ba* ‘hail’.

The data in this article are based on Suzuki (2019b). This article aims to provide a more detailed explanation of specific word forms. First, I provide an overview of the word forms for ‘sow’ in Section 2, followed by those for ‘boar’ in Section 3. Each

overview summarises general observations and analyses key forms. Section 4 discusses a potential origin of the word forms in question.

2. Geographical variation of ‘sow’

Suzuki (2019b:46–48) describes the lexical variation for ‘sow’ in Tibetic languages in the eastern Tibetosphere, summarised as 16 lexical forms classified into four groups. Of these, this article focuses on the types with a MA-affix, namely: R+MA, MA+R, R+MA+M, and R+MA+MA. Here R denotes a root, and MA and M denote affixes. Figure 1, using the same dataset as Suzuki (2019b), illustrates the four types and their distribution.

Fig. 1 Word forms for ‘sow’ with a MA-affix.

Type R+MA is mainly attested in varieties of three areas:

- Sharkhog, dPalskyid, and Thewo (Eastern Section; Tournadre 2014).
- Central Khams, but their distribution is scattered.
- Southern Khams (Sems-kyi-nyila and sDerong-nJol groups).

Of these three, the last area also has varieties using other types, MA+R, R+MA+M, and R+MA+MA.

Type R+MA is analysed as a derived form consisting of *phag*, the general term for ‘pig’, and *ma*, a female-determining suffix. As mentioned in Section 1, *ma* is attested in LT with the same function. Type MA+R, *ma phag*, takes the reverse order of *phag ma*; however, it is not attested in LT. LT *ma* functions as a suffix in principle, and therefore its use as a prefix does not derive from LT.

Note that a semantic subclassification has occurred in some restricted areas in Yunnan, that is, ‘sow without piglets’ and ‘sow with piglets’, as mentioned in Tshering Yangdrön and Suzuki (2021). In such varieties, Type R+MA (*phag ma*) is used for ‘pig-mother’, denoting ‘sow with piglets’ (see Appendix). In this case, we can consider another morphological interpretation of Type R+MA; the suffix *ma* designates ‘mother’ rather than ‘female’. The word for ‘mother’ is generally *a ma*; other forms such as *ma* and *ma rgan* are also attested in limited varieties. In sum, the morpheme *ma*, identical to the female-determining suffix, is used for ‘mother’.

Referring to the interpretation of the morpheme *ma* as ‘mother’, we analyse Type MA+R, *ma phag*, as a form consisting of the morpheme *ma* ‘mother’ and the root *phag* for ‘pig’. This interpretation can be applied to the rest forms to be discussed, Types R+MA+M and R+MA+MA. Type R+MA+M contains oral forms corresponding to LT *phag + ma + mo* (Suzuki 2019b), and this is analysed as a ‘pig’ + ‘mother’ + female-determining suffix. The morphological analysis of Type R+MA+MA is similar, that is, it is a form consisting of LT *phag + ma + ma*: ‘pig’ + female-determining suffix + ‘mother’.

I summarise the present analysis as follows:

- 1 basis: forms corresponding to LT *phag ma*, ‘pig’ + female-determining suffix;
- 2 re-interpretation: forms corresponding to LT *phag ma* with an interpretation of the morpheme *ma* as ‘mother’, which is not attested in LT;
- 3 development: forms based on the re-interpretation, adding another morpheme to emphasise ‘female’.

We note that a semantic subclassification of ‘sow’ as ‘sow without piglets’ and ‘sow with piglets’ functions as a background triggering Stage 2.

3. Geographical variation of ‘boar’

Suzuki (2019b:42–46) describes the lexical variation for ‘boar’ in Tibetic languages in the eastern Tibetosphere, summarised as 35 lexical forms classified into six groups. Of these, this article focuses on the types with a PA-affix, namely: R+PA and PA+R. Figure 2, using the same dataset as Suzuki (2019b), illustrates the two types and their distribution.

Fig. 2 Word forms for ‘boar’ with a PA-affix.

Types R+PA and PA+R are only attested in the southernmost area of Khams, in varieties belonging to the Sems-kyi-nyila group.

Type R+PA (*phag pha*) is analysed as a derived form consisting of *phag*, the general term for 'pig', and *pha*, the morpheme for 'father'. Therefore, Type PA+R (*pha phag*) shows an order of morphemes the reverse of that in Type R+PA. Though we find both morphemes in LT, we do not find these combinations in LT. The literary translation is 'pig-father' or 'father-pig'.

4. Discussions

Comparing the word form for 'sow' with that for 'boar', we can, to some extent, trace semantic changes and processes from 'sow' to 'pig-mother'. However, it is not easy to interpret the development of the word form for 'boar'. To examine a potential interpretation for the case of 'boar', I create a synthetic map from Figures 1 and 2. Figure 3 displays the relationship between 'sow' and 'boar', indicating three types in the Legend as follows:

- F = the word form for 'sow' including *ma* and that for 'boar' not including *pha*;
- FM = the word form for 'sow' including *ma* and that for 'boar' including *pha*;
- N/A = the word form for 'sow' not including *ma* and that for 'boar' not including *pha*.

Fig. 3 Synthetic map of word forms for 'sow' and 'boar'.

As discussed in Section 2, the interpretation of the form *phag ma* as 'pig-mother' is based on a re-interpretation of the LT suffix *ma*. This suffix only has a female-determining function. From the LT perspective, it is erroneously analysed as the same morpheme 'mother', but from the geo-linguistic perspective, this phenomenon is a creative re-interpretation. Based on this process of semantic change, the form *phag pha* or *pha phag* for 'boar' can be understood as formed by analogy from 'sow' as 'pig-mother'. These two forms are recorded in DTLF (1899:621), noted as 'non-castrated pig', which probably reflects the use in the varieties of Eastern Tibet; refer to Suzuki (2019a) for the dialectal feature of DTLF (1899).

Lexical change due to re-interpretation and analogy requires motivation and condition (Iwata 2017, 2020). In the present case, I assume that the new interpretation of *phag ma* as 'pig-mother' originates from the necessity to distinguish 'sow without

piglets’ from ‘sow with piglets’ in some varieties. This distinction is also recorded by Giraudeau and Goré (1956:295), the description of which reflects the use in varieties of Eastern Tibet.¹ It is highly probable that the necessity to distinguish the identity as ‘mother’ from that as ‘female’ triggered the semantic re-interpretation of a female suffix as a morpheme denoting ‘mother’, yielding the interpretation of the form *phag ma* as ‘pig-mother’ as a result.

The distribution of the three types indicated in Figure 3 suggests that the form *phag pha* or *pha phag* is related to *phag ma* as ‘pig-mother’. The varieties using *phag pha* or *pha phag* for ‘boar’ also use *phag ma* for ‘sow’. Hence, the formation of the forms containing the morpheme *pha* ‘father’ has resulted from analogy: parallelism to the word formation of its female counterpart *phag ma* ‘pig-mother’. The LT morpheme *pha* does not function as a male-determining suffix, but only denotes ‘father’. Thus, the interpretation of *phag pha* is limited to ‘pig-father’.

Note that the given analogy is a morphological process at the morphemic level. It differs from anthropomorphic animal terms. In Tibetic languages, there are expressions such as *a rgya spre’u* ‘Brother Monkey’ or simply ‘monkey’ and *a khu dom* ‘Uncle Bear’ or simply ‘bear’ (See Tournadre and Suzuki 2021 for more examples). Compared with these examples, the form *pha phag* ‘boar’ is a single word, not a term of address like ‘Father Pig’.

In sum, the two word forms *phag ma* and *phag pha* or *pha phag* are morphologically in parallel; however, their formation process did not occur in parallel but consecutively. The re-interpretation first occurred in the form *phag ma* for ‘sow’, and then the analogy was applied to ‘boar’, the male counterpart, producing a parallel form to the re-interpreted form of *phag ma* ‘pig-mother’.

These semantic changes and morphological processes are only attested in the Tibetosphere in Yunnan. Varieties using the form *phag ma* are also distributed in Gansu and Sichuan; however, as far as the present data are concerned, there are no varieties using *phag pha* or *pha phag* for ‘boar’. Since the form *phag ma* exists as a LT word for ‘sow’, it is possible that it is used in the same sense as LT in oral varieties.

5. Conclusion

This article analysed the specific word forms for ‘sow’ and ‘boar’ that consist of the root *phag* ‘pig’ and morphemes representing ‘mother’ (*ma*) and ‘father’ (*pha*). Of these, the form *phag ma* exists in LT, originally analysed as *phag* ‘pig’ and *ma*, a female-

¹ In this article, I do not discuss why the distinction was needed in the given varieties.

determining suffix. However, in many varieties in Yunnan, the form *phag ma* is re-interpreted as *phag* ‘pig’ and *ma* ‘mother’ following the necessity to distinguish ‘sow without piglets’ from ‘sow with piglets’. However, some dialects in these varieties further developed through analogy a parallel form to *phag ma* for the male counterpart ‘boar’: *phag pha* or *pha phag*, consisting of *phag* ‘pig’ and *pha* ‘father’. The present examples exhibit semantic changes and morphological innovations seen from the geolinguistic perspective of Tibetic languages.

Appendix

Pig-mother (sow) and her child (piglet) at nDawpa County (Kandze Prefecture, Sichuan).

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